

PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF GENDER STEROTYPE ON TEACHERS' COMMITMENT TO DUTY IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE

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Abstract

The study determined the relationship between gender stereotype and commitment to duty by teachers with specific focus on senior secondary school teachers in Maiduguri, Borno State. To achieve this, two objective and hypotheses were tested. Survey and correlation research designs were used for the study. The target population comprised of 726 teaching staff selected from nine schools. A simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 363 teachers. A self-developed questionnaire instrument and time book were used for data collection. The instruments were validated and pilot-tested using the split half method which yielded a reliability co-efficient of 0.78. Data collected were analysed using standard deviation, frequency count and percentage for demographic information. Inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of statistical significance. The findings indicated a positive significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers commitment of duty. The study then recommended that among other things, there should be a mechanism set up by the education ministry to monitor teachers commitment to service.

Keyword: gender, stereotype, commitment, competence.

Introduction

There is no educational system that can rise above the level of its teachers. This is because teachers play pivotal roles in providing education to the students. Every school strives to recruit qualified teachers that can deliver quality education to the learners. The fact remains that teaching and learning depends on the teachers as there can be no meaningful socio-economic development in any country without teachers. In the view of Ogunyika, Okeke and Adedoyin, (2015) even if the educational planners have the best education policies and design, the government votes the largest sum of its revenue to education, the ultimate realization of the aims of education depends on the teachers.

It is therefore expected that only teachers with necessary academic background, professional competence and positive character traits can translate to action, the basic pedagogical principles which constitute the bedrock of a sound and progressive system of education. Teachers act as the proof for transmission of intellectual traditions and technical skills from one generation to another and help to keep the touch of civilization burning. In addition to this, a teacher is a distinctive individual who is capable of transmitting educational policies. For this reason, the teaching profession should be handled by competent and qualified persons to avoid putting the nation into a mess.

Considering, the extent to which teachers are important, a high level of commitment is expected of them. As used in this context commitment to teaching denotes loyalty, steadfastness and devotion to duty by the teacher. A committed teacher is supposed to pose a sense of competency. It is a natural ingredient to the teaching profession. While educational qualifications are important, a knowledgeable teacher without dedication to teaching may not sustain quality education (Manning and Patterson, 2005). According to Allen (2000) stereotype is associated with the development of beliefs concerning the traits supposedly possessed by most members of society. This implies that the impact of stereotype tends to change the individuals perception of reality over a period of time. Gender stereotype in its own narrows the possibilities for discovery of what truly exists within a male and a female.

Gender stereotype can affect the level of commitment of a teacher to teaching. It becomes a problem when forces in profession and the society arbitrarily assign expected roles of male and females in the profession. At the higher levels of education, where the position of teachers have a higher status, the number of females involved decreases (Spade, 2001). This communicates a very powerful message that female are more likely than male to teach young children and to have positions with little power and intellectual authority. This, to some extent, might affect their level of productivity. It is against this background that this study seeks to establish the relationship between gender stereotype and teachers commitment to duty in Maiduguri, Borno State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine the relationship between;

- i. Gender stereotype and competence in teachers among teachers in Maiduguri metropolis.
- ii. Gender stereotype and compliance to ethical standards of professionalism in Maiduguri Metropolis.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between gender stereotype and competence in teachers among teachers in Maiduguri metropolis?
- ii. What is the relationship between gender stereotype and compliance to ethical standards of professionalism in Maiduguri Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The two research questions were hypothesized and tested at 0.05 level of significance

H01: There is no significant relationship between gender stereotype and competence in teachers among teachers in Maiduguri metropolis.

H02: There is no significant relationship between gender stereotype and compliance to ethical standards of professionalism in Maiduguri Metropolis.

Theoretical framework

This study utilized The Theory of Career Choice by John Holland (1997). The theory asserts that gender is an important predictor of peoples attraction to different activities, and professions. The theory claim that both individuals and work environments can be categorized and then matched to each other according to the type of work they are most interested in. This means that people who choose to work in an environment similar to their personality type are more likely to be successful in their career.

The significance of this theory to our investigation is that it offers a precise analysis of the variables of gender stereotype and individuals career choice. The theory can help the research in relating teaching success to gender. Since how people act and feel at work depends, to a large extent, on their work place, if one is working with people who have a personality, trait like his, one will be able to do many of the things they can do, and will feel most comfortable with.

Gender Stereotype and Teacher's Competence to Teaching Profession

As more people began to appreciate the role of teachers in the society, according to Plato's educational design, the highest officer in the state should be minister of education. In his view, educational should be a socialization process to make an individual righteous, truthful and good. To achieve this, he opined that all schools should be adequately staffed with trained teachers. He also advocated that teachers should be handsomely rewarded. With the emergence of universities and other diversification of schools during the medical period, teaching then became more complicated and the status of the teacher more enhanced. It then became more evident that a teacher cannot perform up to expectation unless he or she is trained for the job. The trend continued until the present time, in that pre-service training is now a pre-requisite for any professional teacher.

To butters the point above, Okeke (2003) carried out a study to examine the possible influence of teachers' qualification on teaching effectiveness of curriculum student achievement in Enugu State. Two hundred (200) teachers

with various qualifications were used for the study. The result shows that students taught by qualified teachers performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified teachers but no significant differences in academic performance of students taught by experienced teachers and inexperienced teachers. The component of professional ethics became a standard for measuring a professional teacher.

Similarly, Mark (2005), conducted a study title, “Trained and untrained teachers perception of important competencies for effective teaching of French: Implication for effective implementation of secondary French language curriculum”. The study used 90 French language teachers in Enugu and Ebonyi state secondary schools. The instrument for data collection was a competency rating scale containing 50 competency items develop for the study. The result showed that significant differences exist in competency items between the professionally trained (B.A/French teachers). The result also revealed that the professionally trained teachers teach better than the untrained teachers.

Also, Abubarkar (2006) carried out a study on teacher and student factors as correlates of achievement in integrated science. He studied the extent to which eleven variables predict achievement in Integrate Science. Fifty-two (52) Integrated Science teachers and seven hundred JSS 3 students were selected from twenty-six within-three local government areas in Kaduna state. The researcher employed five instruments for data collection which include teachers' knowledge of objective question, teaching strategies and assessment practices questionnaires, teaching strategies positive correlation between the eleven predictor variables. When taken together and the criterion variables (achievement in Integrated Science), eight out of the eleven variables contributed significantly to achievement in Integrated Science. The standard regression weights associated with each variable reveals the order of contribution: teaching strategies (0.265), assessment practices (0.184), teacher's knowledge of the objective (0.120), area of specialization (0.100), teaching experience (0.100). The study showed no significant effect of teacher's gender on achievement in Integrated Science. The study

recommended that specialists are needed for meaningful outcomes in our educational systems.

In addition to that, Emeke and Odetoyinbo (2003) carried out another study on teacher factors: as determinants of achievement in teaching. They sampled forty teachers and five hundred students from twenty schools within six education zones in Oyo State. The integrated science objective scale (ISOS) Teaching Strategies and Assessment Practices Questionnaire (TSAPQ) and Integrated Science Achievement Test (ISAT) was used for data collection. The results showed that knowledge of the objective of the programme ranked higher (5.246%) at 0.05. qualification of the teacher also contributed significantly (3.173%) in the criterion variable. From the seven predictors, sex had direct effect with only teachers' gender having indirect effect.

Udeinya (2008) and Okafor (2006) also reported that male teachers are more competent than their female counterparts in implementing geography and mathematics curriculum in secondary while (Omoogun, 2009) reveals that gender significantly affects teachers' competency need of environmental education concepts.

Peters (2007) described the framework for analyzing a task-based component to include: the problems of recognizing competent experts in the field of interest especially in the specific tasks and sub-tasks. Today's teachers are expected to be flexible to adapt to changes in learners' readiness. To do this, they need to be equipped with all kinds of professional teaching style and be able to utilize the right style at the right time to the right audience and in the right place. (Adedayo, 2016)

As a way of improving the professional competence of teachers in response to the needs of a globalized-knowledge economy, (Obanya, 2010) proposed that professional teaching should now emphasize qualitative transformation of the learner and therefore, should be built around the principles of transformational pedagogy.

Gender Stereotype and Teachers' Compliance to Ethical Standard of Teaching Profession

In the present global educational scenario, schools are expected to provide more information on their educational qualities of which the effective teachers form the central and integral component. (Adesina, 1977) posits that teachers should make the education of their pupils their first concern and are accountable for achieving the highest possible standards in work and conduct. Ethics for the teaching profession represent a vision of professional practice and teachers are accountable for achieving the highest possible standards in work and conduct, teachers act with honesty and integrity; and should have strong subject knowledge, keep their knowledge and skills as teachers up-to-date and are self-critical, this becomes pertinent in view of the recent developments in education, such as increased in demanding and active parents or students, implementation of ethical standards of teaching and government policies on the development. No educational system can rise above the level of its teachers and teachers can either make or mar the society, (National Policy on Education NPE, 1986).

According to Reyad and Aldmour, (2017), ethics are long life human product, which form the most important social control of individuals, where their manners should comply with the rules, criteria, traditions and habits of the profession, society, organization, groups or institutions. The professional rule stemmed from the honor and ethical practices and agreements, such as the profession of education. In their study, the sample consisted of 131 principals and 65 supervisors. The researcher developed a questionnaire of 55 items. After it was verified in terms of confidence and stability, it was distributed over the sample, which constituted 50% of the study population. The study concluded some results mainly that the degree of teachers' commitment of the code of conduct and ethics of profession was medium as perceived by principals and supervisor. The results also showed that there were statistically significant difference ($\alpha < 0.05$) attributed to the profession position for the favor of principals.

Nevertheless, there is unanimous agreement in scholarly writings that it is important to make certain key ethical principles explicit in the formation of morally responsible practitioners, such as fairness, empathy, honesty and patience, by dealing with them in formal teaching and guided reflection. Strand of research by (Bruce and Marina, 2016) on professional Ethics Education for Future Teacher. The result of the research reveals that ethics should be part of teacher education both converging strands of research and reflection and that led to a new found appreciation for making ethics an integral part of the university-based education of teachers the profession's ethical norms is a basic requirement of professionalism and professional practices.

Methodology

Research Design

Correlation and survey research design was used in this study. Nworgu, (2015) stated that, the correlation and survey method is used to gather data at a particular point in time with the intention of describing the existing condition or identifying standards against which existing condition can be compared.

Population and Sample

The target population for this study is made up of all the 726 (seven hundred and twenty six) teaching staff of 9 (Nine) public Senior Secondary School in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State. However, fifty percent (50%) of the target population which is 363 (three hundred and sixty-three) teachers was drawn as sample size through simple random sampling technique, this is because using it is possible to generalize the findings that are representative of the whole population (Wanda, 2011).

Research Instrument

The instruments used for data collection in this study are; researcher's self-developed questionnaire captioned; Gender Stereotype and Teachers' Commitment to Teaching among Maiduguri Senior Secondary Schools Teachers (GSTCTAMSSST), and time books. The questionnaire was divided

into two (2) sections. Section “A” and 'B” Section. “A” contains the respondents' bio-data while Section “B” contains the questionnaire items.

Procedure for Data Collection

An introductory letter was also taken to the principals of the selected schools to seek for their permission and support to make all appropriate communication with school officials in order to obtain reliable and adequate information for the study before questionnaires were administered to the respondents (teachers). The researcher assured the respondents that any information given would be kept confidential and would only be used for the purpose of this study alone. With the help of a trained research assistance, questionnaires were administered to the respondents (teachers) by the researcher personally in the sampled schools and were collected later.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for this study was statistically organized, described and analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, frequency counts, and percentage for both the respondents' demographic information and research question and inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test formulated hypotheses at 0.05 statistical level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 4.1: Gender of the Respondent

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
Male	184	50.7	50.7
Female	179	49.3	100
TOTAL	363	100	

The result in table 4.1 shows that 50.7% of the respondents were male while 49.3% of the respondents are female. This implies that majority of the respondents are male.

Table 4.2: Educational Qualification of the Respondent

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
NCE	195	53.7	53.7
OND	12	3.3	57
HND	34	9.4	66.4
Degree	120	33.0	99.4
Master	2	0.6	100
TOTAL	363	100	

The results in table shows that 53.7% of the respondents are NCE holders, while 33% of the respondents graduates. The study also revealed that 9.4%, 3.3% and 0.6% of the respondents are holders of HND, OND and Master Degree respectively. This means that majority of the respondents in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State are holder of NCE.

Table 4.3: Years of Service of the Respondent

Years of service	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
11 – 20	110	30.30	30.30
21 – 30	114	31.40	61.70
31 – above	139	38.29	100
TOTAL	363	100	

The results in table shows that 38.29% of the respondents are between the 31-above of age in services, while 31.40% of the respondents are between the 21-30 ages in service. The study also revealed that 30.30% of the respondents are between the ages of 11-20 in service. This implies that about one-third of the total respondents in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State are at the age of retirement.

Table 4.4: Age Bracket of the Respondent

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
51 and above	17	4.7	4.7
41 -50	41	11.3	16.0
31- 40	137	37.7	53.7
20 – 30	168	46.3	100
TOTAL	363	100	

H₀₂: There is no relationship between Gender Stereotype and Teachers Competence in Teaching in Maiduguri Metropolis Borno State, Nigeria

Table 4.5: Pearson Moment correction statistic showing relationship between Gender Stereotype and Teachers Competence in Teaching in Maiduguri Metropolis Borno State, Nigeria

Variable	Df	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Gender stereotype	361	179.84	20.90	0.851	.000
Teachers competence		29.38	5.23		

Above table shows the Pearson product moment correlations analysis. An understanding of the computed Pearson product moment correlation statistic above revealed that ($r=0.851$, $p=0.001$) thus showing a positive significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers competence in teaching at Maiduguri Metropolis Borno State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers' competence in teaching in Maiduguri metropolis Borno state, Nigeria is hereby rejected.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between gender stereotype and teachers compliance to ethical standards of profession among Maiduguri Secondary School teachers, Borno State, Nigeria

Table 4.6: Pearson Moment correction statistic showing relationship between Gender Stereotype and Teachers Compliance to Ethical Standards of Profession among Maiduguri Metropolis Borno State, Nigeria

Variable	Df	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Gender stereotype	361	179.85	20.90	0.884	0.000
Teachers competence to ethical		32.56	6.03		

The above table shows the Pearson product moment correlations analysis. An understanding of computed Pearson product moment correlation statistics above revealed that ($r=0.884$, $p=0.001$) thus showing a positive significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers compliance to ethical standards of profession among Maiduguri secondary school teachers, Borno State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers' compliance to

ethical standards of profession among Maiduguri secondary school teachers, Borno State, Nigeria is hereby rejected.

Discussion

Hypothesis One revealed that there is positive significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers' competence in teaching, Maiduguri Metropolis Borno State, Nigeria.

The findings agreed with that of Mark (2005) which revealed that significant difference exists in competency items between the professionally trained (B.A/French teachers). The result further revealed that the professionally trained teachers teaching is better than the untrained teachers. Similarly, (Ugwu, 2007) showed that teachers' qualification (academic and years of teaching experience had a significant effect on their use of the MEINST). The mean score (29.19) of students in experimental group c whose teacher held M.Ed. Industrial Technology Education was higher than the mean score (26.9) group A whose teachers held HND and TTC.

The findings of this study also is in agreement with the study carried out by (Okeke, 2003) which revealed that students taught by qualified teacher performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified teachers but no significant differences in academic performance of students taught by experienced teachers and inexperienced teachers.

Hypothesis Two revealed that there is positive significant relationship between gender stereotype and teachers' compliance to ethical standards of professionalism among teachers in Maiduguri Metropolis. This is in line with findings of Reyad and Aldomour (2017), which revealed that ethics are long life human product, which form the most important social control of individuals, where their manners should comply with the rules. The study concluded some results mainly that the degree of teachers' commitment to the code of conduct and ethics of profession was medium as perceived by principals and supervisors. The results also showed that there were statistically significant difference ($0 < 0.05$) attributed to the profession position for the favor of principals. The ethics of teaching demands that a teacher must have his

lesson plan before teaching, best teaching comes about from having a good lesson plan. Preparation and planning are a critical component of effective teaching. If anything, every teacher should be over prepared.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from this study, the researcher concluded that teacher's competence and compliance to ethical standards of professionalism are significantly related to gender stereotype. This implies that gender stereotype has negative effect on teachers' commitment to teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Teaching service Board should enhance the mechanism that would monitor teachers' competence to teaching to ensure punctuality
2. Ministry of Education should make recruitment and promotion of teachers to be strictly based on proper training (qualification) and quality performance.
3. Ministry of Education should emphasize on teachers of operate professionally when teaching.

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